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Chromium(III) Mixed Chelates containing 2-(2'-Pyridyl) Benzimidazole

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2-(2'-PYRIDYL) benzimidazole (PBzH)¹⁻⁴ can function as a neutral bidentate NN donor(I) and as a monobasic bidentate NN donor(II). Reaction

of this ligand with $K_3[Cr(NCS)_6]$ gives a mixed ligand complex⁵ $[Cr(PBzH)(NCS)_2(OH)(OH_2)] 1.5 C_2H_5OH$. Binuclear halobridged complexes of the type $[Cr(PBz)_2X]_2$ ($X = Cl, Br$) have also been reported⁴. We report three new mixed ligand complexes $[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl$, $[Cr(PBz)(o\text{-phen})(tu)_2]Cl_2$ and $[Cr(PBz)_2(dipy)(tu)_2]Cl_2$ ($BigH = \text{biguanide}$; $dipy = \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl; $o\text{-phen} = o\text{-phenanthroline}$ and $tu = \text{thiourea}$). In all the three cases the benzimidazole behaves as a monobasic bidentate NN donor.

Experimental

Tris(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride and trichloro *tris*(thiourea) chromium(III) chloride were obtained by published procedures^{5,6}. 2-(2'-Pyridyl) benzimidazole was obtained by a modified procedure described by Ghosh and Mishra⁷.

Synthesis of $[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl$: 0.9 gm of *tris*(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride was dissolved in hot water. A solution of 0.4 gm of the ligand (PBzH) in alcohol was added to the above solution and the mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 4 hrs. After filtration the solution was reduced to a small volume and was allowed to crystallise in a refrigerator. The crude material was purified from alcohol.

Syntheses of $[Cr(PBz)(o\text{-phen/dipy})(tu)_2]Cl_2$: An alcoholic solution of 1 gm of *o*-phenanthroline (or of 0.8 gm of dipyrldyl) was added to a 1:1 alcoholic solution of 1 gm of $[Cr(tu)_2Cl_2]$. On refluxing for 2 hrs the colour of the solution changed from green to red. About 0.5 gm of PBzH ligand (dissolved in alcohol) was added and the solution refluxed for 10 hrs. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was taken almost to dryness. The pasty mass was taken up in alcohol, concentrated under a fan and allowed to crystallise in a refrigerator.

Results and Discussion

We had earlier shown⁸ that *o*-phenanthroline or α, α' -dipyridyl reacts with *tris*(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride to furnish mixed chelates $[Cr(o\text{-phen/dipy})(BigH)_2]Cl_2$. With 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole a different type of product, $[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl$, is obtained. Its conductivity ($\Lambda_M = 110 \text{ ohms}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$) in methanol indicates a 1:1 electrolytic nature. The magnetic moment ($\mu = 3.7 \text{ B.M.}$) is as expected of a $3d^3$ ion complex. The electronic spectra of the complex reveal a band around 18.2 kK (= 10 Dq), which is assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transition. The 10 Dq value is, however, lower than those⁹ observed for several other $[CrN_6]$ complexes e.g.:

$[Cr(BigH)_2]^{3+}$ (20.7 kK); $[Cr(en)_3]^{3+}$ (21.8 kK); $[Cr(NH_2)_6]^{3+}$ (21.5 kK). Deprotonated 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole thus appears to be a weaker ligand compared to BigH, en, NH_2 .

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF CHROMIUM(III) MIXED CHELATES

Chelate	Colour	Analyses(%)				H ₂ O	Λ_M^{**}	μ (B.M.)	10 Dq (kK)
		Cr	N	Cl	S				
$[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl \cdot 1.5H_2O$	Brick red	8.8 (8.6)*	25.2 (25.4)	6.2 (5.8)	—	4.4 (4.4)	105	3.70	18.2
$[Cr(o\text{-phen})(PBz)(tu)_2]Cl_2$	Dirty green	7.7 (8.0)	19.5 (19.8)	11.0 (10.9)	10.0 (9.8)	—	154	3.65	17.1
$[Cr(dipy)(PBz)(tu)_2]Cl_2$	Brown	8.0 (8.3)	19.2 (20.1)	11.2 (11.9)	10.5 (10.2)	—	158	3.80	—

* Calculated values are given in parentheses.

** In methanol at $10^{-2} - 10^{-4} M$; $\text{ohms}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$.

Reaction of *o*-phenanthroline or dipyrityl with $[\text{Cr}(\text{tu})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ is known⁶ to produce complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{tu})_2(\textit{o}-phen/dipy)₂] Cl_2 . The reaction of 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole with $[\text{Cr}(\text{tu})_2(\textit{o}-phen/dipy)₂] Cl_2 (prepared *in situ*) gave complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{PBz})(\textit{o}-phen/dipy)(\text{tu})_2]\text{Cl}_2$. It is of interest to note that even a large excess of the ligand PBzH could not displace the two thiourea ligands, which are therefore likely to be *trans* disposed. Only at high dilution ($\sim 10^{-4}M$) in methanol a 2 : 1 electrolytic conductance ($\Delta_{\kappa} \sim 160 \text{ ohms}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) is observed. Magnetic moments (3.6-3.8 B.M.) are normal. Electronic spectra give 10 Dq values around 17-18 kK (${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transition).$$

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Studies on Th(IV) and Zr(IV) Complexes of Oxygen Donor Ligands-III. Pyrazolone Derivatives of Oxozirconium(IV)[†]

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CONSIDERABLE attention has recently been focussed on coordination behaviour of pyrazolone ligands such as antipyrine (Apy) and 4 amino antipyrine (AApy)¹. The isolation and characterization of some new complexes of oxozirconium(IV)

with Apy and AApy are reported in this communication.

Experimental

Antipyrine was obtained from Fluka, while 4-amino antipyrine from Koch-Light Laboratories Ltd. (England). Lewis acids were obtained as reported earlier².

The complexes were prepared by the following general method. Methanolic solutions of oxozirconium(IV) salts were mixed with the ligand in the same solvent in the required molar ratio. The thiocyanato complexes separated out immediately; the perchlorato complex was obtained as a brown-yellow crystalline solid after constant stirring of the reaction mixture for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr; the chloro complexes compound after concentrating the reaction mixture on a water bath while the bromo, iodo and nitrate complexes were obtained after refluxing the reaction mixture for *ca* 2 hr, removing the excess solvent by distillation and treating the residual mass with ether.

The complexes thus obtained were filtered, washed with appropriate solvent and finally with ether and dried in a vacuum dessicator over P_2O_5 .

The analyses and physical measurements of the complexes were made as reported earlier².

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes along with their colour are recorded in Table I. The electrical conductance measurement in nitrobenzene and dimethyl sulphoxide indicate [Table I] that the chloride and bromide complexes are non-electrolytes; nitrate and thiocyanate complexes behave like 1 : 1 while iodide and perchlorate complexes correspond to 1 : 2 electrolytes. The molar conductance measurements of $\text{Zr}(\text{AApy})_2^+(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ indicate it to be a 1 : 3 electrolyte. The molecular weight determination of the complexes also support the same electrolytic behaviour of the complexes except $[\text{ZrO}(\text{AApy})(\text{NCS})_2]$. The cryoscopic molecular weight determination of this complex indicates the formation of 1.5 species per formula unit. This behaviour can be explained provided the formation of three species per two formula units of the complex is proposed as $[\text{ZrO}(\text{AApy})(\text{NCS})]_2(\text{NCS})_2$.

Detailed ir studies of the pyrazolones have been reported recently^{1,2}. Pertinent ir spectra of the complexes show a considerable shift ($\sim 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of carbonyl absorption to lower frequency, indicating a decrease in the stretching force constant of C=O as a consequence of coordination through its oxygen. Thus C=O stretching frequency which occurs at 1660 cm^{-1} in the free ligand has been observed in the region $1550-1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes. Several absorptions associated with C-H out-of-plane deformation modes appear in the range $920-720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in antipyrine^{1,2}. Such absorptions associated with the pyrazolone ring undergo

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